

Information about individuals who commit economic crimes committed in the construction industry

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Annotation: This article is dedicated to one of the most pressing issues today, namely economic crimes committed in the construction industry, in which information about individuals committing economic crimes is provided on socio-demographic, psychological, psychophysiological, biological, and other data, the circumstances that need to be proven in the investigation, and its specifics, the methods of committing the crime, forensic cases of committing the crime, the development of investigative versions, effective planning and conduct of investigative actions, the application of tactical methods, ways of psychological communication with the suspect.

Keywords: construction, economic crimes, investigation, tactical methods, fraud, embezzlement, suspect, accused, civil servants, construction, accounting, economics, management, chief accountant, proctor, head of the production and technical department, socio-demographic, psychological, psychophysiological, biological, investigator, investigator, tactical methods, behavior, model, investment.

Economic crimes committed in the construction industry are inextricably linked to economic relations in society, where the economic interests of the state and the property of individuals are violated. This can disrupt the management of economic activity under the guise of legal activity for the purpose of obtaining material benefits from individuals. Therefore, the identity of the person who committed the crime during the investigation is an important element of the criminalistic characteristics of the crimes. The study of personal characteristics helps to develop investigative versions in the early stages of the investigation, effectively plan and conduct investigative actions, apply tactical methods, and engage in psychological communication with the suspect and accused. The study of the personality of the person who committed the crime has been the subject of forensic research.

Behavioral and other psychological characteristics of a person, as well as

social characteristics: education, skills, interests, help determine the circumstances that need to be proven directly or indirectly during the investigation, the methods of committing the crime. When investigating economic crimes committed in the construction industry, it should be taken into account that the crimes committed are elements of specific criminal activity. In other words, every crime committed constitutes a system of criminal activity. Therefore, as a rule, a person committing an economic crime in this area does not limit themselves to committing multiple crimes, but tries to effectively utilize the conditions that have arisen over a long period of time in order to achieve their selfish goals.

The purpose of committing the crime also arises precisely with the emergence of favorable conditions. When investigating economic crimes committed in the analyzed area, it is also important to study the personal qualities of the person who committed them. Information about the identity of persons suspected or accused of committing crimes, such as socio-demographic characteristics, information about their rank and social status, moral and psychological characteristics, is one of the main issues that should be clarified in the proper organization of the investigation. It is advisable to study the personality traits of individuals who have committed economic crimes in the construction industry, dividing them into two categories.

Specifically, Yu.N. Kuleshov¹ classified the first category as individuals possessing characteristics common to all individuals and committing crimes of this category. Based on this set of personal qualities, it is possible to develop a typical model of individuals who have committed crimes. The second category includes personal qualities that allow for the identification of a specific citizen who has committed a specific economic crime in the field. These personality traits, along with assisting investigative bodies in solving specific crimes, are also useful in identifying the person who committed the crime. Because these personal qualities are reflected in some cases of a committed criminal act, and they are used by investigative bodies in the process of proof.

¹ Кулешов Ю.Н. Методика расследования экономических преступлений в сфере строительства. Автореферат диссертации на соискание ученой степени кандидата юридических наук. Ростов-на-Дону 2020. –С.13. <https://crimescience.ru>

It should be noted that the identities of the suspects serve as an important source of information for investigators. According to E.A. Ivanova, who analyzed crimes committed in the economic sphere, economic crimes, according to socio-demographic characteristics, are crimes characteristic of managerial personnel of organizations with different forms of ownership. Forensic elements related to the identity of officials who have committed robberies in construction organizations can include their age, education, authority, and personality². These individuals possess certain knowledge in the field of construction and have certain administrative, economic, and commanding powers in the organization's activities. Therefore, the main suspects in construction organizations can be the manager, his deputies, chief accountant, managers.

The construction industry claimed that the culprits required special knowledge and skills, especially as it was important for the organizers in developing a criminal scheme, while for other participants, knowledge in the field was not important³. According to him, individuals who have committed crimes of fraud, embezzlement or embezzlement in the construction industry are considered to have organizational skills and sufficient intellectual potential. A.A. Tereshenko also expressed similar thoughts⁴. Within the framework of the investigated criminal cases, the subjects of the crime, i.e., the organizers and direct executors, are the heads and owners of the construction organization. In addition to their gender, age, education, their powers, and personal relationships with civil servants are indicated as elements of criminal significance related to the personality of officials of construction organizations⁵.

Within the framework of the investigated criminal cases, the subjects of the

² Иванова Е.А. Характеристика личности, совершающей экономические преступления // Вестник ТИУиЭ. 2015. №2 (22). URL: <https://cyberleninka.ru/article/n/harakteristika-lichnosti-sovershayuschey-ekonomicheskie-prestupleniya>

³ Безбогин А.К. Организация первоначального этапа расследования хищений в строительстве. Диссертация на соискание ученой степени кандидата юридических наук. Краснодар-2020. –С. 24.

⁴ Терещенко А.А. Сведения о личности преступника, влияющие на тактику его допроса при расследовании мошенничеств в сфере строительства за счет средств федерального бюджета // Искусство правоведения. The art of law. 2022. №1 (1). URL: <https://cyberleninka.ru/article/n/svedeniya-o-lichnosti-prestupnika-vliyayushchie-na-taktiku-ego-doprosa-pri-rassledovanii-moshennichestv-v-sfere-stroitelstva-za>

⁵ Петровиченко Р. В. Криминалистическая характеристика хищений, совершенных должностными лицами строительных организаций. – 2016. <https://elib.psu.by/bitstream/123456789/34880/1/133-136.pdf>

crime, i.e., the organizers and direct executors, are the heads and owners of the construction organization. In addition to their gender, age, education, their powers, and personal relationships with civil servants are indicated as elements of criminal significance related to the personality of officials of construction organizations. The presence of personal relationships and connections between the officials of a construction organization and the heads of other organizations, as well as with law enforcement officers, allows them to conspire to achieve a criminal goal. This is also necessary to circumvent the law, positively resolve the problems of the construction organization related to the law. As a result, those responsible for overseeing the activities of the construction organization in government agencies are cold-blooded in their duties: they are blind to the illegal misappropriation of funds by the construction organization and the provision of false reports.

During the commission of a crime, a person acts under the influence of their personal qualities: level of intellectual development, level of education, personal relationships with officials of state bodies and organizations involved in construction, etc. Socio-demographic, psychological, psychophysiological, biological and other information about the suspect, the accused is formed by the investigator, the investigator during the investigation by sending a request to various organizations, as well as based on the testimony of the participants. Sometimes even through such methods, it may not be possible to obtain the necessary information about the person who committed the crime. This problem is clearly visible when investigating fraudulent crimes committed in the industry. In particular, obtaining a description of the suspect in the construction carried out on the basis of investments at his place of work does not yield the desired result. Because the high profitability of this type of activity encourages suspects not to work in any responsible position in a construction company⁶. Even if they are in a responsible position, the description received from the construction organization is not reliable information. Therefore, the necessary information can be obtained by questioning other suspects and

⁶ Лопатин, С.А. Особенности криминалистической характеристики мошенничества в области инвестиционного строительства / С. А. Лопатин // Вестник Владимирского юридического института. – 2009. – № 4(13). – С. 96-100. – EDN KYIHNH. <https://elibrary.ru/item.asp?id=12992688>

witnesses.

Information about a person suspected or accused of fraudulent crimes committed in the construction industry based on investments or contributions can be characterized as follows: firstly, biological and demographic characteristics: gender, age, psychological state, education, family status, etc.; secondly, legal characteristics: conviction, termination of criminal proceedings against him, previously brought to administrative responsibility for what act; thirdly, characteristic features of his character: individual characteristics of the person. Socio-demographic information about a person suspected or accused of committing a crime does not depend on their personal qualities. According to the results of the study of criminal cases, the following information was collected when studying crimes committed by persons who committed crimes of embezzlement and embezzlement in the construction industry: age: among them, the number of people aged 30-60 is 76 percent, and 18-24 years is 24 percent; gender: men make up 72 percent, women make up 28 percent (women usually work not as leaders of a construction organization, but in their accounting According to the results of the study of the age of the defendants who committed economic crimes in the construction industry, S.A. Lopatin found that the age of those accused of committing a fraudulent crime aimed at obtaining money from others through the creation of a fake company is around 20-25 years.

If we look at the experience of foreign countries, then in the USA, this category of individuals is 36-40 years old. At the same time, in our opinion, the suspects and defendants of fraudulent crimes committed in the construction industry based on investments have a high level of education: according to the study, 22.8% of them had a secondary education and 27.1% had a higher education.

According to N.Yu. Makarova, who studied the criminalistic characteristics of fraudulent crimes committed in the construction of low-rise residential buildings, in order to commit such a category of crime, a person must have life experience, the staff of the organization and experience in working with clients, such qualities and

the necessary level are formed when a person reaches the age of 30-35⁷. The crime of embezzlement and embezzlement in the construction industry can be organized by a person with professional training, a good understanding of the construction industry, and the ability to work with documents. Leaders typically have a higher or secondary specialized education (in construction, engineering, economics) and possess the necessary knowledge in the field of construction or economics. The fact that they have intellectual potential helps to find gaps in legislation and conceal crimes. Furthermore, the proportion of women in the commission of economic crimes committed in the construction industry is low.

According to Zaderanko, at a time when women's social and economic independence in society is growing, there are also cases of their involvement in economic crimes in the field of construction individually or as a group. They are not usually the leaders of a gang⁸. Based on the analysis of the materials of the studied criminal case, the following socio-demographic characteristics can be given based on the available information in criminal cases about individuals who have committed crimes of fraud committed in the field of housing construction: age: among them, the number of people aged 30-60 makes up 77 percent, while the number of people aged 20-30 makes up 22 percent; gender: men make up 73 percent, women make up 26 percent; education: 82 percent have higher education. In addition, this category of suspects and accused of committing a crime possesses a number of psychological qualities, in particular, sufficient professional skills in the field of construction, communication skills, the ability to quickly gain the trust of people, a good psychologist, and the ability to convince the interlocutor⁹.

⁷ Макарова Н.Ю. Методика расследования мошенничества, совершенного в сфере малоэтажного строительства. Диссертация на соискание ученой степени кандидата юридических наук. - Санкт-Петербург, 2014. -С. 60.

⁸ Задерако С.В. Особенности и расследования корыстных преступлений в сфере строительства, связанных с фальсификацией проектно-сметной и отчетной документации. Автореферат диссертации на соискание ученой степени кандидата юридических наук. Ростов-на-Дону – 2013. –С. 18. https://static.freereferats.ru/_avtoreferats/01006665628.pdf?ver=5

⁹ Розин А.Н. Расследование мошенничества в сфере жилищного строительства: диссертация ... кандидата юридических наук : Москва, 2009.-С. 194

Specifically, an analysis of fraudulent crimes committed in the construction industry shows that defendants view engaging in this type of criminal activity as a means of achieving their desired lifestyle, as well as a high material value. This can also be seen from their long preparation for some crimes: From the circumstances of this criminal case, it is understood that a group of individuals initially create a firm and register it in order to achieve their criminal goals. This firm is used for criminal activity. At the same time, individuals formally terminate the marriage so that their family property is not transferred to the benefit of the victims or seized during the investigation to compensate for the damage caused by the crime. However, in practice, the property is owned by the ex-husband or wife. In the early stages of the investigation, information about the methods of committing economic crimes may be insufficient. Such a problem can be solved by studying the personalities of people suspected of committing crimes.

In the investigation of economic crimes in the construction industry, the process of proof is conducted in two directions: the personal side of the person who committed the crime from the methods of its commission; the side of the methods of its commission from the information about the person who committed the crime. In practice, contracting organizations do not fulfill the tasks assigned to them within the framework of the contract at the required level after receiving funds from the state budget. The cashing of these funds is a complex issue, based on accounting rules for their circulation. Therefore, the suspects and defendants have a certain level of knowledge about the methods and procedure for embezzling money. This requires investigators to take a special approach when determining the directions of the investigation, as well as when questioning these individuals. At the same time, almost all crimes committed in the sphere are committed with participation. In this case, establishing compliance with the law regarding the commission of a crime by a group of individuals will have significant forensic significance. It is noteworthy that an official of a state body may also operate within a criminal group. Identifying such cases helps to clarify versions of the methods of preparation for the crime, its commission, and the disclosure of the crime.

In economic crimes committed in the construction industry, the group

typically includes the organizer and performers specializing in performing only certain actions. In order for the organizer not to be held criminally liable, it is in the interest of the group members to be held liable only among the performers.

According to N.V. Toropova, possessing sufficient knowledge and skills in this field, as well as necessary information about the mechanisms of economic crime, requires, in simple terms, intelligence from the organizer¹⁰. It should be noted that a high level of knowledge is not only a characteristic of organizers. According to Kulishev, performers can also have a high level of intellect. In his opinion, he meant a highly qualified accountant and other specialists¹¹. Performers may not have organizational skills, and not everyone has the ability to analytically assess the situation. At the same time, any information about the identity of the accused who committed an economic crime in the construction industry will not be relevant during the investigation. Factors such as attitude towards family, relatives, and behavior do not serve to establish the truth in the process of investigating crimes. Typically, individuals accused of committing economic crimes in the industry try to show their positive side towards those around them. In practice, there are cases where even organizers do not possess qualities such as the aforementioned sociability and even lack sufficient knowledge in the field. However, the position he occupies does not clearly distinguish him from others.

Criminal prosecution of organizers and high-ranking officials in the investigation of economic crimes committed by a group of individuals in the sphere may pose difficulties for investigative bodies. The crime is organized by the group in such a way that the aforementioned persons are not initially suspected by the investigative body. Relationships between group members are built on mutual interest. In some cases, there may be two leaders within the group, rather than one. Such cases are usually possible in cases where an official of a state body is also involved in the group. This leader is a guarantee of the effective conduct of criminal

¹⁰ Торопова Н.В. Психолого-криминалистический подход к изучению преступного поведения и личности преступника // Вестник Томского государственного педагогического университета. 2012. № 6 (121). С. 233-235.

¹¹ KULESHOV Y. N. ИСПОЛЬЗОВАНИЕ СПЕЦИАЛЬНЫХ ЗНАНИЙ ПРИ РАССЛЕДОВАНИИ ЭКОНОМИЧЕСКИХ ПРЕСТУПЛЕНИЙ В СФЕРЕ СТРОИТЕЛЬСТВА.

activity and is responsible for the part of the activities of the construction organization that depends on the decisions of state bodies. Furthermore, the conviction of a person has criminal and forensic significance.

In conclusion, the study of the issue of conviction in the forensic description of economic crimes committed in the construction industry, that is, in the analysis of the identity of suspects and defendants, provides the necessary information for clarifying the mechanism of the crime.

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